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**Crime and Violence Update
in Bangladesh:
An Analysis from BPO**

**Rohingya Crisis: Violence,
Rohingya Armed Groups and
Changing Territorial Control in
Rakhine**

**The Stranded Million:
Rohingyas in Bangladesh and
their Repatriation**

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The Stranded Million: Rohingyas in Bangladesh and their Repatriation

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I. Introduction

This article intends to assess the current state of the nearly 1.2 million Rohingya displaced community who have been living in Bangladesh as a protracted refugee situation since 2017. This was not the first time Bangladesh hosted a Rohingya displaced community who left their country to save their lives. But in terms of the magnitude of the number so far, Bangladesh has been struggling with providing shelter, protection, and livelihoods to over 1.2 million stranded Rohingya communities and also taking various diplomatic measures for their safe return to their home country. This article also explores and provides recommendations for a sustainable solution to their return and the role of international and regional organizations in supporting this measure.

Rohingyas were recognized as the citizens of Burma, as stipulated in the first Constitution of the Union of Burma⁴¹. However, Myanmar has scrapped the Rohingya Muslim minority's citizenship rights.⁴² The Rohingyas predominantly live in the Arakan State of Myanmar; through concerted political measures and

military operations, which are tantamount to genocide and genocidal activities, the Myanmar state forced the Rohingyas to flee to neighbouring Bangladesh⁴³. We argue that refugeehood is not a choice. What makes refugees or the push factors behind someone becoming a refugee varies from one context to another. Discriminatory citizenship policy, oppressive laws, and large-scale violence committed by the state security forces and majority community often create minorities, displaced persons, refugees, and stateless persons.

The issue of displaced persons and refugees got international attention after the Second World War, which uprooted and dislocated an unprecedented number of people, which was roughly 55 million in Europe alone. The leaders of the allied forces (USA, UK, and Soviet Union) realized the problem of dealing with these displaced persons who were unable to return to their homeland due to insecurity and life threats. American President Franklin D. Roosevelt and his wife, Eleanor D. Roosevelt, predicted that the war caused mass-scale problems

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⁴¹ The official English name was changed by the country's government from the "Union of Burma" to the "Union of Myanmar" in 1989, and still later to the "Republic of the Union of Myanmar".

⁴² It may be noted that there are Hindus and Christians also among the Rohingyas in the camps of Cox's Bazar.

⁴³ Amena Mohsin and Mohammad Atique Rahman (2022), *Living with Violence and Trauma: The Case of Rohingya Women in Myanmar and Bangladesh*, Centre for Genocide Studies, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

with human refugees, and a new kind of refugees emerged after the end of WWII who did not wish to return to their home country to avoid death and persecution by their governments. Identifying this critical nature of the refugee problem, Article 14 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) recognizes the right of persons to seek asylum from persecution in other countries⁴⁴. Owing to this principle, the United Nations Convention relating to the Status of Refugees, adopted in 1951, defines 'refugee' (Art. I, 1951)⁴⁵ as someone unable or unwilling to return to their country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion.

Therefore, this convention underlies the responsibility of the international community and the host country towards these persons who fled their home country and cannot return to the same. That includes non-discrimination in providing essential services to the refugees, non-penalization for illegal entry into the host country, and a principle of non-refoulment. The principle of non-refoulment stipulates that they are not expelled or returned to a territory against their will, where they fear threats to life or freedom⁴⁶. Despite the world community duly recognizing the importance of refugee protection and adopting various measures to deal with this matter, at

present, more people are living in refugee conditions than in the post-World War II time. According to estimates by the Office of the UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), 114 million people worldwide have been forcibly displaced (as of September 2023).⁴⁷ That stretches across Ukraine, the Sahel region, Sudan, Afghanistan, Syria, and Myanmar, which doubled the refugee population since 2013.⁴⁸

Although Bangladesh was not a signatory of the 1951 Refugee Convention in 2017, Bangladesh had to open its border and provide shelter to the most significant influx of Rohingya people who had to flee from their country- Myanmar. The August 2017 violence committed against the Rohingya was the culmination of decades of systemic political, legal, and social persecution as well as humiliation inflicted by the Myanmar state. Looking at the nature of violence, one may suggest that it was Myanmar's final solution for its Rohingya people. The United Nations (UN) has termed them as one of the most persecuted people in the world. The August 2017 violence against the Rohingyas in Myanmar made more than 700,000 Rohingyas cross over to Bangladesh⁴⁹. They took shelter in Bangladesh, officially known as the forcibly displaced persons from Myanmar; they live in 34 refugee camps in Teknaf and Ukhiya Upazilla of Cox's Bazar. At present, Bangladesh has been hosting approximately 1.2 million Rohingya since August

⁴⁴ UNHCR (2011), Convention and protocol relating to the status of refugees. URL: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/convention-and-protocol-relating-status-refugees>

⁴⁵ https://www.un.org/en/genocideprevention/documents/atrocities-crimes/Doc.23_convention%20refugees.pdf

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Reliefweb (2024), The refugee and migration situation. URL: <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/refugee-and-migration-situation#:~:text=According%20to%20estimates%20by%20the,refugees%20has%20more%20than%20doubled.>

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ <https://www.worldvision.org/refugees-news-stories/rohingya-refugees-bangladesh-facts>

2017.⁵⁰ According to UNICEF, more than 52 percent are children, which is approximately 683,000 living in the congested and squalid camps in Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh⁵¹. Also, each year since 2017, nearly 35,000 new births have been registered in the Rohingya camps every year. This would mean that since 2017, an additional 150,000 new members have been added to the Rohingya community in 2022.⁵² The local people (or host community) of Cox’s Bazar had set an example of humanity and solidarity towards the Rohingya displaced people by hosting more than one million of them. The long-term Rohingya presence has put tremendous demographic and socio-economic pressures on the host community.

Moreover, since there is no progress on the Rohingya repatriation issue, it further aggravates the situation. In this context, several factors like environmental degradation, economic instability, unequal access to relief and humanitarian assistance, and uncertainty about the recovery of their lands, which are now being used as campsites for the Rohingyas, are some of the factors that may lead to social tension between the host community and Rohingya refugees. In this context, the return of the Rohingyas to their homeland stands at the centre point of the strategic action plan.

⁵⁰Talukder, et.al, (2022), Assessment of Economic Opportunities for Young Rohingyas in Bangladesh. URL: https://rohingyaresponse.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/LSDS-Study-Report_Assessment-of-economic-opportunities-for-young-Rohingyas_November-2022.pdf

II. Historical Review - Rohingya influx in Bangladesh since 1942

The Rohingya influx posed last century's refugee problem for Bangladesh. The first influx took place in 1942. The outbreak of communal violence between the Rakhine and Rohingya communities in Rakhine state resulted in around 22,000 Rohingyas crossing the border of British India and taking shelter in Bengal⁵³. In 1977, the government of Myanmar began Operation Naga Min (Dragon King), which aimed to screen the population. 200,000 Rohingyas fled to Bangladesh, they alleged of being abused at the hands of the Myanmar government and army. In 1978, a massive military

⁵¹ <https://www.unicef.org/emergencies/rohingya-beyond-survival-alert>

⁵² Rahman, M. (2022). The government is worried as the Rohingya population grows fast in Bangladesh camps. The New Age, 11 April 2022.

⁵³ <https://www.hrw.org/reports/2000/burma/burm005-01.htm>

operation forced another 20,000 Rohingyas to seek refuge in Bangladesh. The operation included forced relocation, loot, rape, and vandalization of mosques⁵⁴. They were settled in 13 camps under the UN supervision in Cox's Bazar and Bandarban districts. The government of Bangladesh and Myanmar Junta government started the repatriation program in July 1978⁵⁵. Given this effort, 180,000 Rohingyas returned to their home country between 1978-79⁵⁶. The third wave of influx took place in 1991-92 when around 250,000 Rohingyas entered Bangladesh from Myanmar to avoid persecution and torture by Myanmar's

military in Rakhine state. In 1993, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed between the two governments and the third party called UNCHR (UN High Commission for Refugees). In the next four years (1993-97), over 230,000 Rohingyas returned to Myanmar⁵⁷. From 2012-2015, sectarian violence between the Rohingyas and the Rakhine Buddhist community displaced around 140,000 Rohingyas. In October 2016, followed by the killing of nine police officers, the Myanmar Army launched a clearance operation against the Rohingyas, displacing more than 100,000. Around 74,000 fled to Bangladesh⁵⁸.

As mentioned earlier, Bangladesh is neither a signatory of the 1951 refugee convention nor the 1967 protocol or any regional instruments relating to refugees. However, up until 1992, the Rohingya population in Bangladesh was officially registered as refugees by the UNHCR and GoB. These registered refugees live in two official camps, Kutupalong and Nayapara, in Cox's Bazar district⁵⁹. Since 1992, the Government of Bangladesh stopped registering Rohingyas as refugees in Bangladesh and identified them as "undocumented Myanmar nationals." It is to be noted that before the recent influx since August 25, 2017, 33,000 registered refugees in Bangladesh resided in UNCHR-managed camps. After 2017, the Bangladesh government and the international refugee and relief agencies set up thirty-three camps in Ukhiya

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ <https://reliefweb.int/report/bangladesh/historical-review-rohingya-influx-1978>

⁵⁶ <http://www.msf.org/7979/sites/default/files/old-cms/source/downloads/2002/rohingya.doc>

⁵⁷ <https://www.unhcr.org/media/unhcr-country-operations-plan-2003-bangladesh>

⁵⁸ Amena Mohsin and Mohammad Atique Rahman (2022), *Living with Violence and Trauma: The Case of Rohingya Women in Myanmar and Bangladesh*, Centre for Genocide Studies, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

⁵⁹ Milton et al. (2017), Trapped in Statelessness: Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(8): 942.

and Teknaf Upazilla (see Map-I).⁶⁰ Bangladesh Government recognized them as Forcibly Displaced Myanmar Nationals (FDMN) from Myanmar.

III. Rohingya Repatriation Process

Although Bangladesh is not a signatory to the 1951 convention, the country has adopted all possible measures to ensure the protection, livelihood, and safety of these displaced people from Myanmar. Refugeehood and displacement of a large-scale population is not a one-country problem. The cross-border movement of refugees and displaced people in many countries requires effective collaboration between countries of origin, host countries, and international and regional communities. For example, the Rohingya community in Myanmar, facing decades-long persecution, torture, deaths, and dishonours, embarked on crossing the border to save their lives and dignity.

According to UNCHR, one million Rohingyas were displaced by the internal conflicts in Myanmar to take shelter in neighbouring countries. They are mainly in Bangladesh (860,000), Malaysia (101,000), and India (18,000), as well as smaller numbers in Indonesia, Nepal, Thailand, and other countries⁶¹. The primary objectives of this collaboration are to provide protection and safety for the refugees with dignity and

honour. The secondary aim is to initiate and implement one of the three durable solutions. These are voluntary returns in safety and dignity, local integration, and resettlement to another location or country. Bangladesh, since 1993, has been implementing the first durable solution, i.e., voluntary returns in safety and dignity for the Rohingya displaced people. After the August 2017 influx, the Bangladesh Government initiated the repatriation process. In this context, Bangladesh and Myanmar signed an initial deal for the possible repatriation of the Rohingya to Myanmar on November 23, 2017.⁶² According to the *Guardian*, the deal was based on a 1992/93 repatriation pact between the two countries in which Bangladesh stressed completing the repatriation process within the shortest period⁶³. Myanmar, in this deal, demanded that they would accept Rohingya people with identity documents issued by governments in the past⁶⁴. They also need to fill in forms with the names of the family members, previous addresses in Myanmar, birth dates, and a statement of voluntary return. Identifying the Rohingyas based on two principles, i.e., identity documents and their former residence address as a prerequisite for the repatriation, complicates this process.

First of all, the majority of the Rohingyas are deprived of nationality of Myanmar by its 1982

⁶⁰ <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/95379>

⁶¹ UNHCR (2021), The Displacement and Stateless of Myanmar in the Asia Pacific Region. URL: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/The%20Displaced%20and%20Stateless%20of%20Myanmar%20in%20the%20Asia-Pacific%20Region%20-%20January%202021.pdf>

⁶² S M Ali Reza (2024), Six Years of Rohingya Refugee Crisis in Bangladesh: From Here to Where? *Asia Peace Building Initiative*. URL: https://www.spf.org/apbi/news_en/b_240627.html

⁶³ The Guardian (2017), Myanmar signs pact with Bangladesh over Rohingya repatriation. URL: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2017/nov/23/myanmar-signs-pact-with-bangladesh-over-rohingya-repatriation>

⁶⁴ Ibid.

Citizenship Law. According to this law, there are three categories of citizens, i.e., full citizens, associate citizens, and naturalized citizens. People from the officially recognized national races settled in Burma before 1823. Rohingyas, despite their long history of presence in Myanmar, were not recognized among the eight national races in the 1982 Citizenship Law. They are not even included in 135 other officially-recognized ethnic groups in Myanmar. This Citizenship Act, however, accepts the citizenship of the children if their parents were citizens of Myanmar before the 1982 Act. In this case, Rohingya children born after 1982 may be able to register themselves as citizens of Myanmar based on their citizenship accrued by the 1948 Citizenship Act.

But in reality, the Myanmar authorities, after 1982, refused and restricted registering Rohingya children and also denied their parents Citizenship by issuing colour cards. Over the years,

Rohingyas have failed to obtain new identity cards under the 1982 Law known as Citizenship Scrutiny Cards (CSC). Those who have surrendered their National Registration Cards (NRCs) with their applications to obtain CSC did not have them returned from Myanmar's officials⁶⁶. In 1995, the Myanmar government started issuing Temporary

Images 1 & 2: Identification Cards of Union of Myanmar⁶⁵

⁶⁵ The photo of the identification card was taken by the Author in Refugee Camp no. 13, Balukhali Refugee, Kutupalong, Ukhiya Upazilla, Cox's Bazar, on 24 December 2019.

⁶⁶ Amnesty International (2017), Caged with a Roof: Apartheid in Myanmar's Rakhine State. URL: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2017/11/myanmar-apartheid-in-rakhine-state/>.

Registration Cards (TRCs) or “white cards” (see Images 1 and 2). This card is not proof of citizenship. Instead, it says that the person bearing this card is still in the process of determining their citizenship by the authority. In 2015, the President of Myanmar, Thein Sein, revoked this card and issued a Temporal Approval Card. In this way, the Myanmar government denied the possibility of acquiring full citizenship for the Rohingya people. They are not allowed to own property and stand for election. Therefore, legally, it isn't easy to purchase land in Myanmar. Many of the Rohingyas have no permanent domicile in Myanmar.

Secondly, due to the military crackdown in Rakhine state from 1978 till 2017, thousands of Rohingyas have been displaced either internally or externally. The Myanmar military systematically destroyed hundreds of Rohingya villages to erase the residence addresses of these uprooted people. According to the Human Rights Watch, around 354 villages have been partially or entirely destroyed since August 25, 2017. (See Image.3⁶⁷). It was that time when around 700,000 Rohingyas took shelter in Bangladesh. Therefore, it is tough for the Rohingyas to identify and locate their villages as places/addresses of residence, which is a prerequisite for the repatriation process.

Moreover, before 2017, in 2012, the Myanmar government set up detention camps for more than 140,000 Rohingyas who were internally displaced in Rakhine state due to the ethnic cleansing operations.

Since 2012, they have been confined to open-air prisons (camps) in Sittwe, Rakhine State. According to the Human Rights Watch (HRW) report, these displaced Rohingyas are confined in 24 camps and camps-like settings, where the Myanmar authority restricted their freedom of movement and access to education, primary health care, and humanitarian aid⁶⁸. In this context, the requirements for identification documents have been a contentious issue for the stateless Rohingyas as the Myanmar government has been depriving them of acquiring vital identity and

⁶⁷ <https://www.hrw.org/news/2017/12/18/burma-40-rohingya-villages-burned-october>

⁶⁸ Human Rights Watch (2020), Myanmar: Mass Detention of Rohingya in Squalid Camps. URL:

<https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/10/08/myanmar-mass-detention-rohingya-squalid-camps>.

residency documents, which includes blocking newborn babies from the household lists.⁶⁹ However, voluntary and safe return is the heart of the repatriation process; in reality, the security conditions of Rakhine State are not so conducive due to the ongoing ethnic clash and civil strife between the local people and the army. Tiny numbers of Rohingyas (approximately 1200) have been repatriated so far. Still, these people in Myanmar are living under strict restrictions with no freedom of mobility and are closely watched by the military.⁷⁰

IV. Bangladesh Bears the Burden of Rohingyas:

The Rohingya crisis, now in its seventh year, remains one of the major humanitarian crises of the contemporary world. Nearly 1.2 million Rohingya refugees reside in Bangladesh, primarily in Cox's Bazar and on the island of Bhasan Char, making it the largest refugee camp in the world. This crisis has led to the

development of several significant issues for the refugees, the host communities, and the regional actors, including the countries and international organizations, which are not likely to be resolved shortly and are associated with the future of Bangladesh, Myanmar, and the ASEAN region.⁷¹ The current status of the Rohingya crisis is characterized by a stalemate where the refugees are between the horns of safe and feasible repatriation to Myanmar and the unsustainable and fast deteriorating situation in Bangladesh⁷². The 2023 Joint Response Plan (JRP) for the Rohingya crisis has been proposed at \$876 million as it targets delivering aid to 1.47 million displaced Rohingyas and host communities in Cox's Bazar⁷³. Similarly, the 2024 JRP requests funding of \$852.4 million to assist 1.35 million individuals residing in Cox's Bazar and Bhasan Char, as well as the Bangladeshi host populations in Ukhiya and Teknaf⁷⁴.

⁶⁹ Amnesty International (2017), Caged with a Roof: Apartheid in Myanmar's Rakhine State. URL: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2017/11/myanmar-apartheid-in-rakhine-state/>.

⁷⁰ Saha, K. K. 2023. *Rohingya Repatriation: Caught Between State Failure and Armed Resistance*. Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies. https://www.ipcs.org/comm_select.php?articleNo=5852.

⁷¹ Milton et al. (2017), Trapped in Statelessness: Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. Link: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14080942>; BDNews24 (2024), Rohingya Crisis May Get Deeper for Bangladesh, India in Coming Days: Donald Lu. Link: <https://bdnews24.com/bangladesh/j608t62hfr>; Shahnaz Karin et al (2020), Status of Rohingya in Refugee Camps of Bangladesh: A Review Study, *Open Access Library*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1106575>.

⁷² Brian Gorlick (2019), The Rohingya Refugee Crisis: Rethinking Solutions and Accountability. *Refugee Studies Centre. Working Paper Series*, no. 131. Link: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3506638;

Shamsul Bari (2020), The Rohingya Refugee Crisis: A Time Bomb Waiting to Explode. *Social Change* 50, no. 2 Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049085719901038>; Anas Ansar (2020), The Unfolding of Belonging, Exclusion and Exile: A Reflection on the History of Rohingya Refugee Crisis in Southeast Asia. *Journal of Muslim Minority Affairs* 40, no. 3. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13602004.2020.1819126>; Shahinur Bashar (2021), The Rohingya Refugee Crisis in Bangladesh: Environmental Impacts, Policies, and Practices. Link: https://ir.library.oregonstate.edu/concern/graduate_projects/m326m865f; Hossain Ahmed Taufiq, "Rohingya Refugee Crisis and the State of Insecurity in Bangladesh," *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2107.12080*, 2021, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.12080>.

⁷³ BSS (2023), UNHCR, Partners Seek \$876m for Rohingyas, Host Communities. *The Business Standard*. Link: <https://www.tbsnews.net/rohingya-crisis/unhcr-partners-seek-876m-rohingyas-host-communities-595934>.

⁷⁴ UNHCR (2024), UN and Partners Seek \$852.4m to Support Rohingya Refugees and Bangladeshi Hosts. *UNHCR*. Link:

Since the crisis unfolded in 2017, the plan has been aiming to address many needs—from necessities like food and shelter to more complex issues—such as protection services, education, and livelihood opportunities.⁷⁵

However, the reality on the ground is still grim. Despite rigorous humanitarian efforts, UNHCR found that nearly 45% of Rohingya families need to relish a sufficiently healthy diet, which further causes widespread malnutrition.⁷⁶ In late 2022, it was stated that the financial resources allocated to the food assistance program for displaced Rohingyas in Bangladesh would be reduced.⁷⁷ Due to insufficient funds, the World Food Programme (WFP) reduced food aid from US\$12 per person per month to US\$10 in March 2023 and further down to US\$8 in June 2023.⁷⁸ The World Food Programme (WFP) has been compelled to decrease the food supplies in camps in Bangladesh by 30% due to a significant lack of money. This decision is likely to worsen existing health issues and catalyze the swelling cases of child marriage, child

labour, and gender-based violence.⁷⁹ The allocation of rations was initially intended to be zeroed out in 2024. USAID, conversely, committed to providing a donation that would sustain the program by contributing US\$10 each month.⁸⁰ However, the reduction in rations has already deteriorated food security, as the whole displaced Rohingya population hinges upon humanitarian aid to fulfill their essential survival requirements.⁸¹

When discussing health problems, one has to state that the camps' living conditions are not the best for health purposes.⁸² In this regard, affected refugees experience overcrowding; one million live in crowded and congested places. This dilemma poses adverse consequences to the quality of life of refugees and involves health and safety issues. In addition, the annual monsoon season and the threat of cyclones further composite these risks, necessitating more efforts in disaster risk management and climate change mitigation.⁸³ Also, over 50% of the refugees in the camps are children and youth, being left with a

<https://www.unhcr.org/news/press-releases/un-and-partners-seek-852-4m-support-rohingya-refugees-and-bangladeshi-hosts>.

⁷⁵ BSS (2023).

⁷⁶ BSS (2023) and UNHCR (2024).

⁷⁷ WFP (2024), Bangladesh - Impact of Food Ration Cuts on the Displaced Rohingya Population in Cox's Bazar. *ReliefWeb*. Link: <https://reliefweb.int/report/bangladesh/bangladesh-impact-food-ration-cuts-displaced-rohingya-population-coxs-bazar-may-2024>.

⁷⁸ WFP (2024).

⁷⁹ BSS (2023), *ibid*; European Commission (2024), Food Ration Cuts in Bangladesh: A Year of Struggles and Hope for Rohingya Refugees. *European Commission*. Link: https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/news-stories/stories/food-ration-cuts-bangladesh-year-struggles-and-hope-rohingya-refugees_en.

⁸⁰ WFP (2024).

⁸¹ Christine Pirovolakis (2023), Rohingya Refugees Face Hunger and Loss of Hope after Latest Ration Cuts. *UNHCR*, Link:

<https://www.unhcr.org/news/stories/rohingya-refugees-face-hunger-and-loss-hope-after-latest-ration-cuts>; Crisis Group (2023), Crisis Mounts for Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh. *International Crisis Group*, Link: <https://www.crisisgroup.org/asia/south-asia/bangladesh/355-crisis-mounts-rohingya-refugees-bangladesh>.

⁸² Shahana Afrose Chowdhury and Ayesha Tasnim Mostafa (2020), Rohingya Refugees: Risks and Safety in Bangladesh. in *Citizenship, Nationalism and Refugeehood of Rohingyas in Southern Asia*, ed. Nasreen Chowdhury and Biswajit Mohanty. Doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-2168-3_8; Mallik Akram Hossain, A. K. M. Ahsan Ullah, and Md. Mohiuddin, "Rohingya Refugees in the Pandemic: Crisis and Policy Responses," *Global Policy* 14, no. 1 (February 2023): 183–91, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.13156>.

⁸³ Bapon Fakhruddin, Karunakar Kintada, and Quamrul Hassan (2022), Understanding Hazards: Probabilistic Cyclone Modelling

temporary future. The youngsters, who are deprived of their right to proper education, are not only presently disadvantaged, but they are likely to become a 'lost generation' unable to construct their future in Bangladesh, Myanmar, or anywhere else⁸⁴. In January 2024, UNHCR reported the swelling in the number of Rohingya refugees dying or going missing while escaping Bangladesh and Myanmar by boat journeys in 2023.⁸⁵ Moreover, the security milieu in the camps has worsened in recent years, with reports of provoking violence and criminal activity. The conflicts among the different groups have given rise to more than 100 killings over the past seven years, including the high-profile assassination of prominent Rohingya leader Mohibullah, the chief leader of the Arakan Rohingya Society for Peace and Human Rights (ARSPH), who unrecognized gunmen killed in Kutupalong camp in Cox's Bazar.

for Disaster Risk to the Eastern Coast in Bangladesh, *Progress in Disaster Science*: 100216; Katja Neef, Evan Jones, and Jay Marlowe (2023), The Conflict, Climate Change, and Displacement Nexus Revisited: The Protracted Rohingya Refugee Crisis in Bangladesh. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development* 18, no. 3. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/15423166231190040>.

⁸⁴ Robin E. Al-Haddad, Kendra L. Duran, and Saleh Ahmed (2022), A Lost Generation: Perpetual Education Insecurity among the Rohingya. *Race Ethnicity and Education* 25, no. 6. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2022.2069738>; Rubayat Jesmin (2019), Without School, a 'Lost Generation' of Rohingya Refugee Children Face Uncertain Future. *The Conversation*, Link: <http://theconversation.com/without-school-a-lost-generation-of-rohingya-refugee-children-face-uncertain-future-118805>.

⁸⁵ Gwen Robinson (2024), Rohingya Refugees Signal Despair and Hope in World's Most Crowded Camp. *Nikkei Asia*. Link: <https://asia.nikkei.com/Spotlight/The-Big-Story/Myanmar-s-Rohingya-refugees-signal-despair-and-hope-in-overcrowded-camp>.

V. The 2021 Military Coup in Myanmar and Possible Outcomes of Repatriation:

However, the broader geopolitical context in the region has been shaping the Rohingya crisis. The 2021 military coup in Myanmar has further convoluted prospects for repatriation, as the country is entangled with widespread civil unrest and armed resistance against the junta.⁸⁶ In this respect, the National Unity Government (NUG) has been leading a civil disobedience movement, while various regional 'insurgent' groups and People's Defense Forces (PDF) engaged in violent resistance.⁸⁷ This ongoing politico-economic instability makes safe repatriation impossible in the near term and raises concerns about the long-term feasibility of return even if political environments were to progress.⁸⁸ About this aspect, the international community's response to the Rohingya crisis has been diverse. While there was notable financial assistance—the United States alone provided

⁸⁶ Daniel P. Sullivan (2021), Dire Consequences: Addressing the Humanitarian Fallout from Myanmar's Coup. *Refugees International*; Iqthyer Uddin Md Zahed (2023), Myanmar's Military Coup: The Rohingya Caught 'Between the Devil and the Deep Sea,'. *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism* 23, no. 2: 213–31. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sena.12394>; Adam Simpson (2021), Coups, Conflicts, and COVID-19 in Myanmar: Humanitarian Intervention and Responsibility to Protect in Intractable Crises, *Brown J. World Aff.* 28: 201.

⁸⁷ Chosein Yamahata (2022), Myanmar at a 'Point of No Return': Unity Reborn Despite Junta's Terrorization," in *Demystifying Myanmar's Transition and Political Crisis*, ed. Chosein Yamahata and Bobby Anderson. Doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6675-9_16; Anna S. King (2022), Myanmar's Coup d'état and the Struggle for Federal Democracy and Inclusive Government. *Religions*.

⁸⁸ Anthony Ware and Costas Laoutides (2024), The Rohingya Repatriation Myth: Why Repatriation from Bangladesh to Myanmar Is (Nigh) Impossible, *Development in Practice*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2024.2338213>.

\$1.9 billion in aid between 2017 and September 2022—funding levels have been weakening recently.⁸⁹ Although countries like the United Kingdom, the United States, the European Union, and Australia have imposed economic sanctions on Myanmar’s military junta, these measures have done little to address the Rohingya crisis directly.⁹⁰ However, two endeavours regarding repatriation, in November 2018 and August 2019, failed because no Rohingya were willing to return, mentioning unchanged and unsafe situations in Rakhine State.⁹¹ About this, recent “go and see” visits by Rohingya delegations to camps in Rakhine state’s Maungdaw town have done little to rekindle hope for voluntary and safe repatriation.⁹²

Currently, the situation in Myanmar itself continues to evolve in ways that have not only been impacting the Rohingya crisis but also driving away the focus on repatriation⁹³. The humanitarian crisis has deteriorated further in the country due to the civil unrest, where Rohingya have been trapped between Military operations and ethnic armed groups such as the Arakan Army (AA). There are also reports concerning the forced enrolment of young adults by

the military junta and armed groups, thus adding risks to the remaining vulnerable population in Rakhine State as well as to the displaced ones in Bangladesh.⁹⁴ As per the reports of various human rights bodies since February 2024, Myanmar forces have enrolled more than 1,000 Rohingya Muslim male teenagers and children from camps of internally displaced people in Kyaukphyu, Sittwe, Maungdaw, and Buthidaung townships.⁹⁵ These individuals are reportedly subjected to abusive training sessions lasting two weeks before being deployed to the front lines of the conflict between the junta and the Arakan Army, resulting in numerous casualties⁹⁶. The exploitation of Rohingya by both the Myanmar military and various armed groups and the protracted status of the displaced Rohingyas in Bangladesh highlights the overall vulnerability of the population in the region. This disquieting development violates international humanitarian law and further complicates prospects for safe and voluntary repatriation, making it protracted for many years.

⁸⁹ UNHCR (2024).

⁹⁰ Daniela Gavshon (2024), Australia’s Myanmar Sanctions, a Step Forward. *Human Rights Watch*. Link: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/02/06/australias-myanmar-sanctions-step-forward>; GOVUK (2024), Myanmar Military-Linked Enterprises and Infantry Divisions Sanctioned 3 Years on from the Military Coup. *GOV.UK*. Link: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/myanmar-military-linked-enterprises-and-infantry-divisions-sanctioned-three-years-on-from-the-military-coup>; US Department of State (2024), Burma Sanctions. *United States Department of State*. Link: <https://www.state.gov/burma-sanctions/>.

⁹¹ Nasir Uddin (2023).

⁹² Crisis Group (2023).

⁹³ Robinson (2024).

⁹⁴ Kawsar Uddin Mahmud (2024), Why Has the Myanmar Junta Banned Its Male Citizens from Going Abroad for Work? *The Geopolitics*. Link: <https://thegeopolitics.com/why-has-the-myanmar-junta-banned-its-male-citizens-from-going-abroad-for-work>; Sreeparna Banerjee (2024), Rohingya Crisis: Exploitation, Recruitment, and Challenges. *Orfonline.org*. Link: <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/rohingya-crisis-exploitation-recruitment-and-challenges>.

⁹⁵ Banerjee (2024).

⁹⁶ Ibid.

VI. The Future of Rohingya Crisis and Repatriation: Recommendations

The question of repatriation is one of the vital aspects while we discuss the future of the Rohingya crisis. However, the current conditions in Myanmar make any large-scale, voluntary return of refugees soon doubtful. The 2021 military coup in Myanmar has not only derailed Myanmar's fragile democratic transition but has also aggravated conflicts across the country, including in Rakhine State, where the Rohingya would have been repatriated. The ongoing fighting between the Tatmadaw (Myanmar military) and various ethnic armed organizations, including the Arakan Army in Rakhine State, has spawned a volatile and dangerous environment that is not suitable for Rohingya repatriation.⁹⁷ As one refugee noted, "I want to be in Myanmar tomorrow. But relatives and friends in Myanmar know no peace"⁹⁸. However, in this regard, the role of regional organizations such as ASEAN, BIMSTEC, and BCIM in addressing and taking initiatives to resolve the Rohingya crisis has been inadequate and largely unsuccessful. ASEAN, in particular, has been criticized for its poor response to the coup in

Myanmar and its failure to effectively create pressure on the junta to make safe and sound conditions for safe repatriation⁹⁹. ASEAN could play a more robust and constructive role by expediting dialogue between Myanmar and Bangladesh, providing humanitarian assistance, and supporting efforts to create a conducive environment for repatriation¹⁰⁰. Nevertheless, the ASEAN's decision-making process and the divergent interests of its member states make it challenging to adopt a unified and forceful approach.¹⁰¹

BIMSTEC (Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation) and BCIM (Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar Forum for Regional Cooperation) are other regional. However, like ASEAN, these organizations have thus far played an inadequate role in addressing the crisis's political, human rights, and other dimensions. In this respect, the international community's approach has also been marked as a mix of humanitarian support, diplomatic pressure, and calls for accountability. However, the effectiveness of these efforts was limited by several factors, including donor fatigue, competing global

⁹⁷ Al Jazeera (2024), Rohingya 'Genocide Intensifying' as War Rages in Myanmar's Rakhine: BROUK. *Al Jazeera*. Link: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/6/26/rohingya-genocide-intensifying-as-war-rages-in-myanmars-rakhine-brouk>.

⁹⁸ Sullivan (2022).

⁹⁹ Huong Le Thu (2021), ASEAN Has Risked Too Much in Inviting Myanmar's Junta Leader to Summit. *The Strategist*. Link: <https://www.aspistrategist.org.au/asean-has-risked-too-much-in-inviting-myanmars-junta-leader-to-summit/>; Al Jazeera (2021), Criticism over Myanmar ASEAN Deal with Military Coup Leader. *Al Jazeera*. Link: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/4/25/scant-support-for-in-myanmar-asean-deal-with-military-coup-leader>.

¹⁰⁰ Sadia Aktar Korobi (2024), Rohingya Resettlement: Where Is ASEAN? *Australian Institute of International Affairs*. Link: <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/rohingya-resettlement-where-is-asean/>.

¹⁰¹ Imtiaz Ahmed (2020), Special Issue on the Rohingya Crisis: From the Guest Editor's Desk. *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics* 5, no. 2. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2057891120929570>; Imtiaz Ahmed and Niloy Ranjan Biswas (2022), Prominent Bangladeshi Experts Dr Imtiaz Ahmed and Dr Niloy Ranjan Biswas Author a New Book – Rohingyas in Myanmar and Bangladesh. *Rohingya Khobor*. Link: <https://rohingyakhobor.com/prominent-bangladeshi-experts-dr-imtiaz-ahmed-and-dr-niloy-ranjan-biswas-author-a-new-book-rohingyas-in-myanmar-and-bangladesh/>.

crises, and the challenges of engaging with Myanmar's military regime. One of the critical challenges in resolving the Rohingya crisis is the lack of a comprehensive regional and international strategy. While there were numerous statements of concern and calls for action, there was little concrete progress in resolving the root causes of the crisis or creating conditions for safe and voluntary repatriation. In this respect, the UN Security Council, hampered by divisions among its permanent members, has also failed to take concrete action regarding the safe repatriation of the Rohingya people¹⁰².

Looking at the future, several scenarios are conceivable for the Rohingya crisis and the prospects for their repatriation. In the most optimistic scenario, the international pressure associated with internal changes in Myanmar could bring about meaningful improvements that address the root causes of the Rohingya's displacement¹⁰³. A more realistic scenario is that the crisis will remain protracted for many years ahead¹⁰⁴. In this case, the focus would need to shift toward improving conditions for Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh and other host countries while continuing

to work toward eventual repatriation and third-country resettlement¹⁰⁵.

However, even though there have been some rays of hope, in the current environment, the Myanmar authorities do not possess the capability or the political will to implement Rohingya repatriation¹⁰⁶. By the way, any repatriation efforts must be voluntary. As Human Rights Watch notes, "Rohingya refugees have consistently said they want to go home, but only when their security, access to land and livelihoods, freedom of movement, and citizenship rights can be ensured"¹⁰⁷. In the meantime, the stakeholders should work on improving the conditions—expanding access to education, livelihood opportunities, and healthcare—for Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh and other host countries must be stepped up.

The Rohingya crisis will necessitate long-term focus and commitment from the international community in the future. The media of Bangladesh should prioritize their spotlight on the crisis while dealing with major wars and crises like the Russia-Ukraine War.¹⁰⁸ Still, the prospects for the Rohingya

¹⁰² Joshua Carroll (2019), Why the UN Failed to Save the Rohingya. *Al Jazeera*. Link: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/6/28/why-the-un-failed-to-save-the-rohingya>.

¹⁰³ Michelle J. Lee (2021), Media Influence on Humanitarian Interventions: Analysis of the Rohingya Refugee Crisis and International Media Coverage. *Journal of International Humanitarian Action* 6, no. 1. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41018-021-00108-5>.

¹⁰⁴ Mohammad Zaman (2023), Six Years on, a Solution to the Rohingya Crisis Is Still Elusive. *The Daily Star*. Link: <https://www.thedailystar.net/opinion/views/news/six-years-solution-the-rohingya-crisis-still-elusive-3387131>.

¹⁰⁵ Sm Najmus Sakib (2023), Bangladesh Reiterates Call for Rohingya Resettlement in 3rd Countries. Link:

<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/asia-pacific/bangladesh-reiterates-call-for-rohingya-resettlement-in-3rd-countries/2965874>.

¹⁰⁶ Al Jazeera (2024).

¹⁰⁷ HRW (2023), Bangladesh: New Risks for Rohingya Refugees. *Human Rights Watch*. Link: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/05/18/bangladesh-new-risks-rohingya-refugees>.

¹⁰⁸ Kawsar Uddin Mahmud and Nasrin Jabin (2022), Responses of Bangladesh and Myanmar to the Ukraine Crisis: A Comparative Analysis from a Neo-Classical Realist Perspective. *Southeast Asia: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 22, no. 2. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SEAMJ-02-2022-B1007>.

repatriation are in a dilemma, but not without hope. Essentially, it depends on the international community, regional organizations, and all other stakeholders; they must work thoroughly to ensure the rights and dignity of the Rohingya people, keeping them at the centre of resolving this protracted crisis. On the whole, the below-mentioned recommendations can be suggested in this regard:

1. Priority should be given to creating conditions for safe and voluntary repatriation in Myanmar. The international community, posing substantial pressure on the military junta, should work towards establishing a roadmap for repatriation that includes concrete yardsticks for developing conditions in Rakhine State.
2. Improving education and skills development programs targeting the Rohingya people, mainly young people. In this regard, some specific actions may include offering stipends to Rohingya teachers and students and promoting educational projects, both offline and online educational services.
3. Concerned authorities should improve security in refugee camps through solid coordination. The concerned authorities should develop an investigation and apprehension of armed actors and enhance

coordination among law enforcement inside and outside the camps.

4. Expanding livelihood opportunities for Rohingya refugees, providing freedom of movement and access to employment in certain areas.
5. The regional organizations must play a central role in staging the negotiations among the parties and accelerate the repatriation process in the future. ASEAN, BIMSTEC, and BCIM must play a more proactive role in resolving the Rohingya crisis by pushing forward the steps of repatriation. ASEAN, in particular, could play a robust role in accelerating dialogue between Myanmar and Bangladesh by providing humanitarian assistance and supporting endeavours to create environments conducive to repatriation¹⁰⁹.
6. Advocating for increasing international support for host countries, particularly Bangladesh. With over one million Rohingya refugees, Bangladesh confronts diverse challenges. The international community should increase humanitarian funding, especially in light of the potential dwindling due to donor fatigue and competing global crises—the Russia-Ukraine war and the Palestine-Israel conflict.

¹⁰⁹ Korobi (2024); Dr Imtiaz Ahmed and Dr Niloy Ranjan Biswas (2022).

7. Upholding the discussions of the third-country resettlement options. Although repatriation is still the most preferred long-term solution, increased resettlement options can offer immediate relief for the vulnerable population. The government of Bangladesh can think of the offers that countries like the United States and Canada provide for third-country settlement opportunities in limited ways through their mobility programs, such as Welcome Corps at Work¹¹⁰.
8. And the Bangladeshi government should work on keeping the international focus on the Rohingya crisis. The media outlets, especially in Bangladesh, must prioritize coverage of the Rohingya situation alongside other major global crises¹¹¹.

VII. Conclusion

More than a million Rohingya refugees remain stranded in refugee camps in Bangladesh for more than six years after being displaced from Myanmar. They do not have any legal status as such to claim their better livelihoods and human rights. As Nasir Uddin notes, since Myanmar stripped them of citizenship and Bangladesh does not recognize them even as refugees, the Rohingya exist nowhere in the legal framework of

any state.”¹¹² The government of Bangladesh, Myanmar, and the international community still rest on voluntary repatriation as the most durable solution to this crisis. However, the political and security scenario of Myanmar due to the 2021 coup and the outbreak of civil and ethnic strife pose significant challenges to materialising this policy at present and shortly. The territorial control over Rakhine State, either by the Arakan Army or the government of Myanmar, is crucial in this regard, given that both these entities are not so willing to take back their people from Bangladesh. The future of the Rohingya crisis and the prospects for repatriation are indissolubly associated with the broader political and security developments in Myanmar, the strategies of host Bangladesh, and the obligation of the international community to work to find sustainable solutions. While the instant prospects for large-scale repatriation are still dim and full of pessimism, there is room to advance the lives of the Rohingya in the short term while working towards long-term solutions. Finally, any sustainable solution to the Rohingya crisis must be rooted in the rights and dignity of the Rohingya people themselves, prioritizing their safety and voices at the centre of all negotiations and decision-making processes.

¹¹⁰ AFP (2018), Canada Offers to Take in Rohingya Refugees, Pledges Aid. *Dhaka Tribune*. Link: <https://www.dhakatribune.com/world/146363/canada-offers-to-take-in-rohingya-refugees>; UNB (2023), US to Resettle More Rohingyas from Bangladesh in 2024, *The Daily Star*. Link:

<https://www.thedailystar.net/rohingya-influx/news/us-resettle-more-rohingyas-bangladesh-2024-3495801>.

¹¹¹ Mahmud and Jabin (2022).

¹¹² Uddin (2023).

Annex

Some definitional clarification according to BPO Codebook.

Gunfight. A shootout between law enforcement agencies and criminals, militants, or other irregular forces, including the latter, does not match the definition of a non-state armed group.

Clash. Two-sided violence between groups outside of the context of war or insurgency. Example: supporters of rival political parties fight each other.

Assault. One-sided violence by an individual or small group against another individual or small group. Example: stabbing or shooting of someone by a perpetrator

Fight. Two-sided violence between individuals or small groups. Example: brawl between 3-4 people.

Sexual assault. One-sided sexual violence, such as rape or attempted rape, by an individual or small group against another individual or small group.

Destruction of property. One-sided violence is perpetrated with the intent of damaging property—examples are vandalism and arson.

Mob violence (large group assault). One-sided violence by a mob or large group against an individual or a comparatively small and defenseless group. Examples: the lynching of a thief, looting of shops and houses owned by a religious minority

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